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Roles of Pastoral Counseling in the Choice of a Marriage Partner and Its Impacts on Family Sustainability

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Abstract

The need to ensure that people seek pastoral counseling before choosing a marriage partner is of paramount importance in this complex society, inability to seek pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner has constituted some setbacks to marriage sustainability. The paper identifies the concept of pastoral counseling, the biblical foundation in the choice of a marriage partner, the roles or importance of pastoral counseling, the impacts of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner for sustainable family life, the consequences of avoiding pastoral counseling in the choice of marriage partner, pastoral counseling prerequisite for choosing a marriage partner and encouragement to singles in embracing pastoral counseling in the choice of marriage partner. This paper reveals that pastoral counseling helps in making the right decision in the choice of marriage partner, and builds healthy relationships in courtship and marriage. The consequences for not embracing pastoral counseling in the choice of marriage partners are confusion in the choice of a marriage partner, missing God's will, regret, or disappointment in courtship and marriage. However, the paper stresses the need for improvements in the pastor's relationship and availability with the youths who are still singles, in the same manner pastor's wife should be someone whom singles can easily relate with. Orientation for singles about the difference between pastoral counseling in the choice of marriage partner and premarital counseling is also important for singles to take pastoral counseling in the choice of marriage partner seriously.

Keywords: Roles, Pastoral counseling, Choice, Marriage partner, Family sustainability

Introduction

The issue of marriage is very important in Christendom and society at large; knowing the choice of a marriage partner before entering into any relationship is of great importance. The role of Pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner can never be underestimated. Many people would have been enjoying their marriages if they had sought proper pastoral counseling in their choice of a marriage partner. However, it is expedient for intending couples to submit his/her totality to pastoral counseling before entering into a relationship. This brings boldness and assurance to come to God in the times of trouble and challenges in the home. Therefore, entering into

a relationship without the right pastoral counsel is not ideal because seeking counsel for the choice of a marriage partner has a great impact on sustaining the family life. Furthermore, many families are going through serious pain which can never be discussed by anybody, because of the costly mistake they have made in the choice of a marriage partner this has inadvertently stolen their joy in the home, sometimes some couple looks healthy outside but inside they are unhealthy in their relationship, due to time-to-time bully on each other. Many Christian brothers and sisters today reject counseling and enter into relationships without knowing the effect such a decision will have on them. Today many youths and even married couples are regretting the relationship they had entered into because they refuse to have proper pastoral counseling. The majority of the singles out there do not know that there are certain steps and guidelines to be followed in choosing a marriage partner which pastoral counseling will open one's mind to, that is why many homes lack divine and ordained beauty because they marry outside their divine purpose, timing, and will of God for their life (Oladapo, 2008, p. 22-23). The motivation for this paper is to emphasize the importance and impacts of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner and the challenges befalling singles in courtship and marriage for lack of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner in this present society.

Concept of Pastoral Counseling

"Pastoral Counseling is the utilization of a variety of healing (therapeutic) methods to help people handle their problems and crisis more growth fully and thus experience healing of their brokenness" (Clinebell, 1984, p. 26). The overview of counseling comes from God's interest in caring for the church, to ensure that He puts things in place for them. He sends Jesus Christ; the great shepherd/Pastor into the world, to love and care for His people. Jesus deals with people such as sinners, outcasts, and many others and associates with them, Jesus did not discard anyone who comes to Him. The same ministry He commits to the pastors, to care and counsel the people of God. Macdonald (2016) stated that "Pastoral care and counseling is a ministry of evangelism, teaching, discipleship, and encouragement" (p. 6). This is a clear picture that Pastoral counseling models the lives of counselees into the purpose of God for their lives, and also leads the people by the word of God into eternity. The world is full of ups and downs, Challenges, and crises, which left many people with doubt about what to do. "Pastoral Counseling then comes as ease or relief to the people, since counseling deals with the behavior, attitudes, thought, and beliefs of the counselee; this does not rule the facts that counseling must be placed on the leading of the Holy Spirit and Biblical standard in attending to the problems of the counselee" (Benner, 2015, p. 56). The researcher agrees that the Pastoral counselor should follow the leading of the Holy Spirit in addressing the major issues of life in the counseling process. He must always depend on

God in leading the counselee to know the will and mind of God in choosing a life partner; as human beings, despite all creatures certified good by God. In Genesis 2:20, Adam finds it difficult to get suitable help among the creatures until Eve is created. According to Olaniyi (2004), "God originated marriage for the well being of humans and it must be centered on the Godly counsel in order to locate the missing ribs" (p. 45)

Biblical Foundation for Choice of a Marriage Partner

Marriage, a journey of no return was established by God; marriage institution was the original plan, all about marriage began in the commencement of creation in the Garden of Eden. Therefore, every foundation of marriage must be on the solid rock (God). "God in marriage aims to establish His plan on earth through marriage; this means there is no home that must be without having her foundation being laid on God" (Adediran, 2017, p. 1-2). In Genesis 2:18 (The Lord God said it is not good for the man to be alone. I will make a helper suitable for him" Also in verses 23-25 'the man says this is now the bone of my bones and flesh of my flesh; she shall be called woman for she was taken out of a man. For this reason, a man will leave his father and mother and be united to his wife, and they will become one flesh. The man and his wife were both naked, and they felt no shame. From the above Bible passage, it is understood that Adam was a lucky man, God discovered that he was lonely and needed a companion, so as a lucky man he was he did not need to convince a woman to accept him in marriage, God has perfectly done the work for him. "In verse 23 God does not compel Adam to accept Eve, It was through a willing heart he accepted the woman, this means that God can never force a woman or man on anybody though He would surely give direction in ordering one's steps" (p.1).

Nakedness, as seen in Genesis 2:25, implies that they were not ashamed to behold the nakedness of each other. Ogheneakpobo (2015) opined that "both Adam and Eve do not have anything to hide from each other again, the kind of marriage God wants for everyone is an excellent and unique one that is devoid of hidden secrets whether good or bad, palatable or unpalatable, pleasant or unpleasant" (pp. 19-20). Nakedness in marriage brought trust between the spouses. It also determined the wellness, happiness, and blessedness of every marriage. Furthermore, Jesus continues the image of the scripture in the New Testament where He speaks of Himself as the bridegroom (Luke 5:33-35). Jesus provided comparatively little instructions on marriage. "He affirmed the permanent nature of marriage in no uncertain terms; comparing Bible Passages. Genesis 1:27 and Matthew 19:6 give the understanding that Jesus knows the implications of marriage to be a sacred bond between a man and a woman which is established by God Himself" (Kostenderger, 2010, p. 52).

Also, the teaching of Paul from Ephesians 5:21-33. Paul gave the details of marriage to be set within the larger context of God's end-time restoration all things under the headship of Christ, thus Christ's relationship with the Church provides the pattern for

Christian marriage. Meanwhile, the writer of Hebrews indicates that marriage still has an ethical place in the life of the redeemed fellowship (Hebrew 13:4) from (Romans 7:1-3), marriage is seen as a lifetime covenant, it is a sacred agreement between a man and a woman, "It is also a permanent indissoluble union which must not be subjected to man's interpretation but a divine truth because of its deep interpretation that is beyond any human imagination" (Olayoku, 2005, p. 23). Adams (1983) also reiterated "that the church has ignorantly assumed of having the full understanding of the teaching and has not taught the biblical facts and this has made many couples build their homes on worldly standard" (p. 9). Therefore, the marriage relationship is held as God's ordained institution, an institution to bring a love of God and salvation to humankind under the headship of Christ the Lord.

Roles of Pastoral Counseling in the Choice of a Marriage Partner

Seeking counsel in all situations of one's life is a very important decision in the life of a believer, especially in the area of choosing a life partner because no one knows where, when, under what circumstances, and how God will lead one to the right person, Ecclesiastes 4:9-10 says two are better than one.

1. Pastoral counseling helps in the areas where one is confused concerning the issue of choice of life partner, that is "consulting a person who is known to be a strong committed Christian who may be praying along and talk issues over will help to shed light on the confused area and lead one to get the right conviction" (Omojola, 1994, pp. 47-48).
2. It helps to set the priority right in the choice of life partner, some youth today believe that asking and seeking God's face for a life partner comes first but knowing the source and foundation of every good partner which is God is the first priority; after the issues on the salvation of souls have been settled, then comes the prayers on choosing a life partner
3. Another truth on the roles of pastoral counseling is that, "it helps spinsters and bachelors to understand that it is only in Christ that a woman can be free to fulfill her potential when married unlike other religion of philosophy that treat women as inferior" (Osinowo, 2011, pp. 104-105).
4. It guides a spinster or bachelor on how to pray on his/her marital matters; with interaction with a counselor, counseling may lead one to know how God speaks because there are diverse ways through which God speaks to His own children.
5. Another role counseling play in the life of single is that, it helps on how to make right choice of spouse and also liberates singles from all forms of physiological, emotional, spiritual, physical and social trauma and problems.
6. It helps singles to prepare for the task in marriage, since proper understanding of what marriage is and what marriage is not will be discussed during counseling and also

liberate singles on how to live during courtship and to understand better the “dos’ and don’t” in courtship.

7. Pastoral counseling also helps singles to trash out issues that could cause or become problems in their marital life (Oladeni, 2004, pp. 76-78).

8. Collins (2007), submits that “pastoral counseling, helps singles to build stable marriages and healthy families, this means that singles at times are afraid of marriage and as result be reluctant to enter into marriage relationship because of the experience he /she might have seen in the relationship of their relatives but counseling play a very good vital role in helping the unmarried to have stable home and healthy family” (p. 501).

Impacts of Pastoral Counseling for the choice of marriage partner for Sustainable Family Life

Ukarke (2006) stated that “pastoral counseling is important venture in life and it is always good for believers to start all ventures with God, Prov. 3:5-6 says “Trust in the Lord with all your heart and lean not into your own understanding in all your ways acknowledge Him and he will direct your path”. Therefore, getting God involved in plans to get married is a step towards success” (p. 34)

1. Field (1986) opined that “counseling helps couple to have healthy relationship and no one, even the marriage therapist will be able to understand the magnetism such a couple are like giant electromagnets drawing each other into their own magnetic field as a result of unhindered time spent together” (p.16).

2. Sylvester Ogbeneakpobo (2015) in his own opinion discussed that “one of the impacts of counseling on family sustainability is to open couple’s eye and enlightened them that sensitive decision should be made together by the spouses bearing in mind that the man ought to play a guiding role that will lead to making right decision for the good of the home” (p. 19). The researcher agreed with Sylvester on this point so as to eradicate making the same mistake Eve made in Genesis 3:6

3. Counseling also helps couples to understand that the blame game will not help matters, it can only complicate issues. Human beings are bound to make mistakes (p. 19). As for marriage, to free one mind is to accept one’s fault and see how to find solution together in order to move forward and enjoy peace and progress.

4. Furthermore, counseling helps couples to demonstrate true and unconditional love. True love usually ushering home into an atmosphere of ever increasing conjugal bliss, with the help counseling couple will understand that it is only true love that can glue them together in bearing consequences together (p. 20).

Consequences of Avoiding Pastoral Counseling in the Choice of Marriage Partner

Avoidance or neglects of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage has led to the followings

1. Wrong Choice of Marriage partner: The inability of singles to seek for pastoral counsel has led many singles to choose wrongly, because they did not consent to the leadership of the Holy Spirit to seek for right pastoral counseling guidance
2. Confusion in the choice of marriage partner: Lack of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner has resulted to destabilized mind whereby choosing of a marriage partner is like a child play without a serious commitment from both sides. Sometime both parties might be subjecting their courtship to test whether it will work or not because they are not that sure.
3. Missing of God's will: It is easy to miss the choice of God for one's life if care is not taken by seeking proper pastoral counseling in the choice of marriage partner. Some couples homes has been destabilized, some are just managing themselves they do not really enjoy the peace of God in their home because they choose by their own understanding, not allowing proper pastoral counseling in the choice a marriage partner.
4. Disappointment in Courtship: Many singles have disappointed God by not being sincere and faithful God in luring themselves to sin of fornication, and through these some impregnate each other because their choice of a marriage partner was not really guided by pastoral counseling, consequently removing the fear of God in their courtship.
5. Marriage Crises: "Some of the reasons why there a lot of divorce, infidelity, adultery in marriages today starts from not seeking proper pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner" (Oladapo, 2016, p. 59). Many so called Christian homes have crashed landed, many wives have become single mothers likewise the husband. The children are not enjoying their parenthood and some children are now hanging out with bad friends to keep their company since their homes are in disarray.

Pastoral Counseling Prerequisite for Choosing a Marriage Partner

The issue of choosing a marriage partner is so crucial that knowing God's will about it is of great importance that entails one to be really sure that a person one intends to share his/her life with is the one that God has in mind for one life. The reason is that, no one can fully understands the details of the life of another person except God, therefore involvements in pastoral counseling before making a choice of marriage partner is crucial matter that must not be handled with levity hand. The followings are pastoral counseling pre-requisite a spinster or bachelor must follow in choosing a life partner.

1. "A brother/sister who is seeking God's face in choosing a life partner must be connected to the source of all good partners that is "God", this means that such a person must be a child of God, a disciple of Christ, someone who has cordial relationship with Christ and must be sincerely busy with kingdom business" (Shoremi, 2002, p. 23).

2. He/she must be ready to submit to the order, leading and the will of God because it is only God who knows the right and best marriage partner for His people. "The Bible says look not on his countenance or the height of his stature: because I have refused him; for the Lord sees as not the man sees, for man looks on the outward appearance, but the Lord looks on the heart, anyone who submits himself/herself to God's will, shall never err; he/she will enjoy the guidance of God" (Ogunlade, 2005, pp. 5-6).

3. He/she must be matured: Such a person must be matured in the following major aspects of life

(a). Physical Maturity: A person who is physically matured in such that he/ she is not a kid or a child, he must be of right mind who knows right from left, be able to think well and have good plan for marriage sustainability.

(b). Spiritual Maturity: The person must have grown and still growing spiritually. He must know the methods and how God deals with him/her.

(c). Intellectual Maturity: This is the ability to know and understand people, problems and situations without relying on other.

(d). Social Maturity: This has to do with the ability to relate well with people and interact well

(e). Financial Maturity: A brother or sister must be economically and financially stable; he/she must have stable income and able to solve the problem in the family. 1 Timothy 5:8 says. If any one does not provide for his relatives and especially for his immediate family, he has denied the faith and his worse than unbeliever (Oladapo, 2008, pp. 23-24)

(4). The brother or sister must Know how God speaks to him/her; God speaks in diverse way to His children, a spiritually inclined person must be able to discern because God deals with individuals based on their level of understanding of God's knowledge such as the, Bible: Psalm 119:105; Still voice; 1 king 19:11-12, Dream, visions and Revelation; Genesis 37: 5-9, Discerning spirit/ Prophecy; Act 16:16-18, Circumstances; Jonah 2:1-10, Heart conviction; Mathew 4: 18-22, Audible voice; Number 12: 18-22, and Message/Preaching' 1 Corinthians 2:4-5.

(5). Prayer: Waiting on God through prayers is another pre-requisite for choosing a life partner; hence prayer is the key to obtaining the gifts from God.

(6). The word of God: He/she must key himself/herself into study the word of God and understand well the standard of God for choosing a life partner.

(7). Avoid setting standard or idol in heart; Ezekiel 4:1-4 says some of the elders of Israel came to me and sat down in front of me, then the word of the Lord came to me "Son of man, these men have set up idols in their hearts and put wicket stumbling blocks before their faces, should I let them, this is what the sovereign Lord says; when any Israelite set up idols sin his heart and put a wicked stumbling block before his face and then goes to a prophet, I the Lord will answer him myself in keeping with great idolatry. Whatever a

person cherish in an individual whether physical or spiritual could become idol that would gain all the attention of such person and this could eventually influence the choice of life partner. Every one seeking for God's will in marriage must be of clear mind, and must be ready to submit to His leading in discernment.

(8). The person must avoid match-making and writing of names for prophet to choose God's choice.

(9). "Pride and self confidence should be avoided instead he/she should be humbled and fear God" (Ogunlade, 2005, pp. 5-6)

Pastoral Counseling towards Conviction in the Choice of a Marriage Partner

Omojola (1994) suggests some fundamental principle that can help in getting confirmation and to test conviction.

"According to him in looking for conviction, the devil or personal ego can interfere and cause confusion or pass wrong message. The following will be directions for conviction.

1. Consistency: What are revealed by God must follow in sequence and in uniformity, not zigzag, when there is confusion, one need to continue to wait on God until there must be correlation in any message, vision, dream and revelation that are revealed by the Lord.

2. Compatibility: Since marriage is a spiritual relationship, spiritual compatibility must influence the quality of one's choice and relationship.

3. A deep sense of contentment: In getting God's conviction, the divine contentment will fill the heart of the fellow if indeed it is God who is speaking, when it is revealed and received, there will a deep satisfaction in such hear; it is this contentment that keep the spouse to be loyal to each other after wedding,

4. A deep sense of gratitude and thankfulness towards the giver: Human experience has proved that when something desperately needed is given; such heart will be filled with gratitude and thankfulness, which finally accomplish with the peace of God" (pp. 49-54).

Encouraging Singles to embrace Pastoral Counseling in the Choice of a Marriage Partner

Bad experiences/ encounters some singles have had with some pastors may have caused avoidance of pastoral counseling in the choice a marriage partner; however the singles can be encouraged through the following ways:

1. Prayer: Prayer as it says is the master key. Since marriage is the institution created by God, devils as it is known is the greatest enemy and antagonist to every good things which includes marriage relationship because as Gods is interested in marriage relationship, so also is the devil, "therefore pastors should always intercede for

bachelors and spinsters so that their minds will be opened and release themselves for counseling” (Adams, 1983, p. 1).

2. Availability of the counselors (Pastors): Adams noted that marriage relationship and counseling is often the catalyst for individual growth (p. 1). “Many pastors today do not have time to counsel the youth, they are pre-occupied with church activities and meetings, and they do not have counseling hour. Biblical counseling is all about discovering the people’s problem and solving it. If then a pastor/counselor is not available, and sensitive, how then can the problem be solved” (MaCarthur, 2005, p. 101).

(3). Pastor and his wife relationship with the youth in the church: Everybody needs friends who can care and cherish them. Bachelors and Spinsters also need care and good relationship from pastors and their wife, “this serves as source of encouragement to them and give them a sense of belonging, but many ministers instead of relating with them will desert and live them uncared for like sheep without shepherd. Therefore pastor should always build good godly relationship with their members because this will enable the singles to see them as their spiritual and caring father” (p. 101).

(4). Pastors should organize seminars and program on the important of counseling in the choice of a life partner.

(5). There should be teachings on danger of self confidence and choosing a life partner without the proper seeking of counseling.

(6). Parents also should always encourage their children to seek proper counsel before embarking on journey of marital relationship.

(7). Minister/ Pastors should have good approach: manners of approach is very important in every relationship, minister of God should curtail kind of approach that will make members to always come to them and not be judgmental because it may serve as source of discouragement.

(8). Churches should establish marriage committee that will see to the affairs of youth especially in the area of choosing life partners and this should consist of church members who are spiritually inclined and whose home are of good model to the youth

Conclusion

The paper discussed the concepts of pastoral counseling, biblical foundation in the choice of marriage partner, roles of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner and its impacts for family sustainability, it has looked at importance or perception of people about pastoral counseling in choice of a marriage partner, the impacts and consequences of pastoral counseling in the choice of a marriage partner and pastoral counseling for the choice of marriage partner. However concerted efforts of pastors are needed to encourage the singles to embrace pastoral counseling before they choose the person to marry, and singles should know the different between

seeking pastoral counseling for the choice of marriage partner and premarital counseling.

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